

ORION / Trapezium

Table of Contents

<i>Preface</i>	2
<i>ORION April Meeting Information</i>	3
<i>ORION in the Community</i> by David Fields	6
<i>ORION Last Month</i>	9
<i>April Sky Map</i>	10
<i>Recent Astrophotography</i> by Don Spong	12
<i>Astrophotography of Naked-eye Stars and their Fields</i> by Ted Barnes	14
<i>Close</i>	18

Who we are:

ORION was founded in April 1974 by a group of scientists at the United States Department of Energy facilities in Oak Ridge, Tennessee. Our original goal was to perform correlated, instrumented observations of atmospheric and astrophysical phenomena. Since then we have expanded in many directions, including optical and radio astronomy and instrument design and construction.

Future Events:

ORION Monthly Meeting
Monday 17 April 2023, 7 pm

See pp.3-5 for details.

TAO Notes:

ORION people are invited to arrive early with binoculars and / or telescopes to prepare for evening observing and to share refreshments. Please consider bringing a red flashlight or a headband with a red light, in addition to refreshments. All first time visitors should drive to the site before dark.

Map:

<http://www.roanestate.edu/obs/visit.htm>

ATTENTION:
Public stargazes at TAO:
Details on p.3.

Trapezium Submissions

may be sent to:
Editor,
182 Burley Nelson Ln,
Clinton, TN 37716-6024
or by email to *ted dot barnes2 at yahoo dot com*. MSWord or text files and jpg images are preferred.

ORION Monthly Meeting Format

Our monthly meeting will generally proceed as follows:

- Welcome
- Announcements
- Program presentation and response
- Astrotechnology
- Astrophotography

There will usually be time available at the beginning of the meeting for any announcements of general interest.

Please plan to stay until the end of the meeting. We hopefully will all enjoy astrophotography, and “round table” discussions of the techniques used in capturing astronomical images.

Information about ORION & TAO

May be found at the following URLs:

<http://www.orioninc.org/>

<https://orionastronomy.wordpress.com>

<https://www.facebook.com/ORIONAstronomyTN/>

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/454645124557215>

<https://www.facebook.com/pages/Tamke-Allan%20Observatory/120477734665841>

<https://www.roanestate.edu/?349-Tamke-Allan-Observatory>

<https://www.roanestate.edu/pages/obs/index.html>

<https://twitter.com/TAOremote>

Public Stargazes

The dates and times of these events, which are open to the public, depend on local sky and atmospheric conditions and so cannot be scheduled long in advance. The announcement of these events will be made through the ORIONastronomy email list. One may sign up for email notification at no charge at the email address

ORIONastronomy@groups.io

Title: Astrophotography: My Journey, with Cats (Part II, finale)

Speaker: Ted Barnes

Bio: Dr. Barnes received his BSE degree from the University of Michigan at Ann Arbor, and his MS and PhD in theoretical high energy physics in 1977 from Caltech. After a series of international postdoc and research fellow positions, in 1989 he was appointed the first Joint ORNL-UTK Collaborating Scientist, with the ORNL Physics Div. and the UTK Dept. of Physics and Astronomy. His professional research interests involved quantum chromodynamics (QCD; quarks and gluons) and the strong interaction, hadron physics and spectroscopy, applications of QCD to nuclear physics, computational physics, quantum magnetism and neutron scattering, including theoretical and experimental studies of high- T_c analog materials at the HFIR and at RAL. He has over 150 publications and reports in these fields, and is an APS Fellow.

After ORNL and UTK he joined the Office of Nuclear Physics (NP) at DOE HQ in Germantown, Md., where he served as an NP Program Manager for about a decade. On retirement from DOE in late 2018 he returned to the Oak Ridge area, and has since been improving his techniques in astrophotography.

Abstract: Recent developments in the technology available to amateur astronomers and astrophotographers have made it possible to record familiar subjects such as bright nebulae and galaxies in improved detail, and to image surprisingly faint and obscure objects. In two separate presentations (Jan and Apr 2023) Dr. Barnes will discuss his personal experiences with and results in astrophotography, from his first images of out-of-focus tree leaves in Germantown, Maryland in 2015, through more recent images of interesting stars, open clusters, globular clusters, nebulae, galaxies, quasars, and small bodies in the solar system. In this final (Part II) presentation he will concentrate on asteroids and TNOs (trans-Neptunian objects) that he has imaged in Tennessee, and will conclude with his recent attempts to estimate limiting magnitudes from images of faint TNOs and very distant globular clusters. The cats who have assisted him in this work will also be acknowledged.

Meeting Info: Monday 17 April (usual venue) RSCC/Oak Ridge, McNalley Bldg. City Room (A-111) at 7 PM. A Zoom session is open at the link

<https://us02web.zoom.us/j/88528735960?pwd=KzY4bnBHcjlhTzg3L3pOcjY0TFovUT09>

April 17 ORION Presentation

Dr. Barnes, with some of his results in astrophotography since the beginnings in 2015 while at DOE HQ in Maryland.

NGC891 – TAO, 2022

Tree leaves out of focus
Germantown, MD, 2015

M31 with foreground stars removed – TAO, 2022

Astronomy in Tennessee
Lost Ridge Observatory (LRO), nr. Clinton, TN
with Frannie (L) and Bucky (R) - 2019

Dr. Ted Barnes

ORION in the Community (Astronomy, Education, Outreach)

by David Fields

Vice President's Vision, April 2023

First, congratulations to Ted Barnes for accepting the position of Editor of the ORION Trapezium. And thanks to Noah Frere for serving as our Editor for the last couple of years. We're one of the few public-membership scientific organizations, one of the few (the only?) local scientific organizations with a newsletter, one of the few Astronomy groups with a working relationship with a college and an observatory, *etc.* The Trapezium is how we communicate to members, students, friends, and our at-large community.

Why? From the Trapezium:

ORION's mission is to support scientific research, teaching, and amateur astronomy in East Tennessee. We are accordingly closely associated with and support the Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO) through hosting their public events, sharing our knowledge of the skies using a variety of telescopes, and helping to provide intellectually stimulating programs. ORION works to share the wonders of the cosmos and the culture of science with people from all walks of life.

So how well are we doing with our Mission? In an informational sense, very well – we hold informative meetings at the Roane State Oak Ridge Campus, support the Astronomy classes at the college, and schedule/support stargazes (for Astronomy class, the college, and the public). The Trapezium keeps us in touch with science, especially astronomy. With the collapse of local newspapers in covering local educational and scientific topics, the Trapezium has become even more important. As to coverage – the Trapezium needs to reach more people.

What's been happening recently? Several things – for example, here is Allan Poole's photo of the TAO sky on March 27, both a public stargaze and a class night.

Early on we saw Mercury, Jupiter, Mars, Venus, our Moon, and the Sun with spots and prominences. Here are class members with Noah, Ted, John, and Sunny the Astrodog.

Let's consider what else happened that evening.

Noah deployed the solar (H-alpha) scope early.

I had the 8" refractor and binocs / compass going and found Jupiter / Mercury near the horizon, then some brighter objects. I'm in the above photo as well, behind the camera.

Sunny the Astrodog is searching for Sirius, and the dimmer stars of Canis Major.

Later, we saw much more.

John brought his Unistellar telescope (shown above – a neat thing).

DR opened up the LX-200 and found deep sky objects.

Larry showed us beautiful views of the sky, including Uranus.

Since it was a class night, I brought along a Tesla coil and in the classroom, discussed spectrometry and demonstrated the spark spectra of several gases (a neon discharge tube is shown here). Most of us participated in a classroom demonstration of the (shockingly rapid) propagation velocity of an electric field.

Without a newsletter, who would have known about our fun that evening?

Are we doing more? Yes, monthly ORION meetings (last month's together with FORNL), Board meetings, etc. Here's a photo taken at our April Board meeting / picnic. Shown are Ted, Don, Rob, Juan, and David. Jim and Yoko are nearby. Thanks to Jim, Betty, and the Magic Wok for hosting us for this meeting! Juan got two lunches!

The Trapezium, ORION news and stargaze announcements arrive via email to members and friends. We welcome new members.

ORION Last Month:

Last month's presentation, "Asteroid Exploration by the Dawn Spacecraft," on 20 March 2023, was jointly sponsored by ORION and FORNL, the Friends of Oak Ridge National Laboratory. The presenter was Hap McSween, a distinguished planetary geologist and National Academy of Sciences member with a long and distinguished career at the University of Tennessee.

The presentation, which concentrated on the Dawn spacecraft and its discoveries at Ceres and Vesta, was clearly exciting to both audiences. Space exploration is an ever popular topic, especially with the recent progress on Artemis, and the discussion included both general questions about asteroid exploration past and future and detailed technical issues, such as xenon ion propulsion and the surface temperature of Vesta.

McSween's presentation was reviewed by Carolyn Krause in The Oak Ridger, which highlighted the discoveries that Ceres has a young water-ice volcano, and that major impact craters on Vesta suggest that it is the source of an anomalously large number of terrestrial meteorites. Plans for future asteroid exploration include a visit to the asteroid 16 Psyche, which may consist of an exposed metallic core. (Images c/o Carolyn Krause, The Oak Ridger.)

Dr. Hap McSween

The water-ice volcano on Ceres

Hap receives his ORION speaker's mug.

About the Celestial Objects

Listed on this page are several of the brighter, more interesting celestial objects visible in the evening sky this month (refer to the monthly sky map). The objects are grouped into three categories. Those that can be easily seen with the naked eye (that is, without optical aid), those easily seen with binoculars, and those requiring a telescope to be appreciated. **Note, all of the objects (except single stars) will appear more impressive when viewed through a telescope or very large binoculars.** They are grouped in this way to highlight objects that can be seen using the optical equipment that may be available to the star gazer.

Tips for Observing the Night Sky

When observing the night sky, and in particular deep-sky objects such as star clusters, nebulae, and galaxies, it's always best to observe from a dark location. Avoid direct light from street lights and other sources. If possible observe from a dark location away from the light pollution that surrounds many of today's large cities.

You will see more stars after your eyes adapt to the darkness—usually about 10 to 20 minutes after you go outside. Also, if you need to use a torch to view the sky map, cover the light bulb with red cellophane. This will preserve your dark vision.

Finally, even though the Moon is one of the most stunning objects to view through a telescope, its light is so bright that it brightens the sky and makes many of the fainter objects very difficult to see. So try to observe the evening sky on moonless nights around either New Moon or Last Quarter.

Astronomical Glossary

- Conjunction** – An alignment of two celestial bodies such that they present the least angular separation as viewed from Earth.
- Constellation** – A defined area of the sky containing a star pattern.
- Diffuse Nebula** – A cloud of gas illuminated by nearby stars.
- Double Star** – Two stars that appear close to each other in the sky; either linked by gravity so that they orbit each other (binary star) or lying at different distances from Earth (optical double). Apparent separation of stars is given in seconds of arc (").
- Ecliptic** – The path of the Sun's center on the celestial sphere as seen from Earth.
- Elongation** – The angular separation of two celestial bodies. For Mercury and Venus the greatest elongation occurs when they are at their most angular distance from the Sun as viewed from Earth.
- Galaxy** – A mass of up to several billion stars held together by gravity.
- Globular Star Cluster** – A ball-shaped group of several thousand old stars.
- Light Year (ly)** – The distance a beam of light travels at 300,000 km/sec in one year.
- Magnitude** – The brightness of a celestial object as it appears in the sky.
- Open Star Cluster** – A group of tens or hundreds of relatively young stars.
- Opposition** – When a celestial body is opposite the Sun in the sky.
- Planetary Nebula** – The remnants of a shell of gas blown off by a star.
- Universal Time (UT)** – A time system used by astronomers. Also known as Greenwich Mean Time. USA Eastern Standard Time (for example, New York) is 5 hours behind UT.

Easily Seen with the Naked Eye

- Capella Aur • The 6th brightest star. Appears yellowish in color. Spectroscopic binary. Dist=42 ly.
- Arcturus Boo • Orange, giant K star. Name means "bear watcher". Dist=36.7 ly.
- Sirius CMa • The brightest star in the sky. Also known as the "Dog Star". Dist=8.6 ly.
- Procyon CMi • Greek name meaning "before the dog" - rises before Sirius (northern latitudes). Dist=11.4 ly.
- Castor Gem • Multiple star system with 6 components. 3 stars visible in telescope. Dist=52 ly.
- Pollux Gem • With Castor, the twin sons of Leda in classical mythology. Dist=34 ly.
- Regulus Leo • Brightest star in Leo. A blue-white star with at least 1 companion. Dist=77 ly.
- Vega Lyr • The 5th brightest star in the sky. A blue-white star. Dist=25.0 ly.
- Betelgeuse Ori • One of the largest red supergiant stars known. Diameter=300 times that of Sun. Dist=430 ly.
- Algol Per • Famous eclipsing binary star. Magnitude varies between 2.1 & 3.4 over 2.867 days.
- Aldebaran Tau • Brightest star in Taurus. It is not associated with the Hyades star cluster. Dist=66.7 ly.
- Polaris UMi • The North Pole Star. A telescope reveals an unrelated mag 8 companion star. Dist = 433 ly.
- Spica Vir • Latin name means "ear of wheat" and shown held in Virgo's left hand. Dist=250 ly.

Easily Seen with Binoculars

- M38 Aur • Stars appear arranged in "pi" or cross shape. Dist=4,300 ly.
- M36 Aur • About half size of M38. Located in rich Milky Way star field. Dist=4,100 ly.
- M37 Aur • Very fine star cluster. Discovered by Messier in 1764. Dist=4,400 ly.
- M44 Cnc • Praesepe or Beehive Cluster. Visible to the naked eye. Dist=590±20 ly.
- M3 Cnc • Easy to find in binoculars. Might be glimpsed with the naked eye.
- M4 Com • Coma Berenices. 80 mag 5-6 stars in 5 deg. Dist=283 ly. Age=600 million years.
- Dra • Wide pair of white stars. One of the finest binocular pairs in the sky. Dist=100 ly.
- M5 Gem • Fine open cluster located near foot of the twin Castor. Dist=2,800 ly.
- M13 Her • Best globular in northern skies. Discovered by Halley in 1714. Dist=23,000 ly.
- M92 Her • Fainter and smaller than M13. Use a telescope to resolve its stars.
- M48 Hya • 12+ stars in 7x binoculars. Triangular asterism near centre. Dist=1,990 ly.
- R Hydrae Hya • Long period variable. Mag varies between 3.0 & 11.0 over 390 days. Brilliant red.
- R Lyrae Lyr • Semi-regular variable. Magnitude varies between 3.9 & 5.0 over 46.0 days.
- 2232 Mon • A large scattered star cluster of 20 stars. Dist=1,300 ly.
- 2244 Mon • Surrounded by the rather faint Rosette Nebula. Dist=5,540 ly.
- M50 Mon • Visible with binoculars. Telescope reveals individual stars. Dist=3,000 ly.
- Cr 69 Ori • Lambda Orionis Cluster. Dist=1,630 ly.
- Double Cluster Per • Double Cluster in Perseus. NGC 869 & 884. Excellent in binoculars. Dist=7,300 ly.
- M47 Pup • Bright star cluster. 15+ stars in 7x binoculars. Dist=1,500 ly.
- M46 Pup • Dist=5,400 ly. Contains planetary NGC 2438 (Mag 11, d=65") - not associated.
- M5 Ser • Fine globular star cluster. Telescope will reveal individual stars. Dist=25,000 ly.
- Mizar & Alcor UMa • Good eyesight or binoculars reveals 2 stars. Not a binary. Mizar has a mag 4 companion.

Telescopic Objects

- Boo • Red giant star (mag 2.5) with a blue-green mag 4.9 companion. Sep=2.8". Difficult to split.
- Cnc • Contains 500+ stars mag 10 & fainter. One of the oldest clusters. Dist=2,350 ly.
- Cvn • Compact nearly face-on spiral galaxy. Dist=15 million ly.
- Cvn • Whirlpool galaxy. First recognised to have spiral structure. Dist=25 million ly.
- Cas • Yellow star mag 3.4 & orange star mag 7.5. Dist=19 ly. Orbit=480 years. Sep=12".
- M64 • Black-Eye Galaxy. Discovered by J.E. Bode in 1775 - "a small, nebulous star".
- Hya • Ghost of Jupiter. Bright blue disk. Mag 11 central star. Dist=2,600 ly.
- Hya • Classic face-on spiral. Discovered in 1752 by Lacaille. In attractive star field.
- Leo • Superb pair of golden-yellow giant stars. Mags 2.2 & 3.5. Orbit=600 years. Sep=6.4".
- Mon • Triple star. Mags 4.6, 5.0 & 5.4. Requires telescope to view arc-shape. Sep=7.3".
- Mon • Christmas Tree Cluster. Associated with the Cone Nebula. Dist=2,450 ly.
- M1 Tau • Beautiful spiral galaxy visible with binoculars. Easy to see in a telescope.
- M81 UMa • Close to M81 but much fainter and smaller.
- M82 UMa • One of the brightest planetaries. Magnitude 10 central star. Dist=2,600 ly.
- 3132 Val • Superb galaxy with supermassive black hole at its core. Dist=53.5 million ly.
- M87 Vir • Sombrero galaxy. Almost edge-on spiral galaxy. Protruding central core.
- M104 Vir • Superb pair of mag 3.5 yellow-white stars. Orbit=169 years. At their closest in 2005.
- γ Virginis Vir •

CELESTIAL OBJECTS

Recent Astrophotography by Don Spong

M88:

Cloudy weather has limited how much one can do recently, but below are several images I've done recently using my Celestron Edge HD with a 0.7 focal length reducer and controlling everything with a ZWO ASI AIR plus computer.

This is the **spiral galaxy M88** as imaged on the evening of March 29 from my front yard. M88 is 50 to 60 Mly away, magnitude 9.6, and about 7 arc minutes across. It was discovered by Charles Messier in 1781, and is an Sbc spiral, in between an Sb (medium wound) and Sc (loosely wound). The spiral arms are well-defined and can be followed all the way to the core. This image was made by stacking about 30 1-minute exposures.

M88 is part of the Virgo Cluster of galaxies, including M87, M86, M49, M60, etc., as indicated in the right-hand figure. There are many other galaxies I look forward to imaging in this part of the sky, and they are in a good position now for me (rising early in the eastern sky), which is a direction where I don't have large trees in the way.

For more see: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Messier_88

Chart reference: Roberto Mura - Own work, CC BY-SA 3.0,
<https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=6508126>

NGC4169, Hickson 69 – “The Box”:

This is an unusual collection of 4 galaxies that align to form the vertices of a nearly exact rectangle. It is the Target of the Month for Sky Watcher telescope’s monthly imaging competition and is a much more challenging target than M88. It is about 200 Mly away, fairly faint (magnitude 12.2) and occupies a tinier region (1.8 arc minutes) of the sky. The image below is the best I’ve obtained, from the evening of April 9, based on 44 1-minute exposures.

View of NGC4169 from my 8” edge HD scope with 0.7 reducer.
White lines show the nearly rectangular shape.

Astrophotography of Naked-eye Stars and their Fields by Ted Barnes

Setting up your telescope and equipment at a dark sky site can sometimes be a daunting experience. My hoped for trip to TAO in March encountered several difficulties that made a trip impossible. As is often the case the weather was bad, and this was combined with problems with my essential equipment transport, a 1999 Honda Odyssey van. An occasional power steering fluid leak that started in October 2022 grew steadily worse, and by March could no longer be treated by “topping up.” So, I had to decline my 40+ mile trip (each way) to TAO in March, pending purchase of a van that had not already been driven as far as lunar orbit. (I have since purchased a 2014 Odyssey in good condition, so TAO trips are on again.)

So, in March I was working from my home “Lost Ridge Observatory” (LRO), trying to find interesting targets despite having more light pollution than at TAO, and equally bad weather. Of course while stuck at home you can do “shopkeeping” exercises such as improving your polar alignment (tricky because my garage roof hides Polaris), practicing guiding techniques, and installing some level of temperature control in the home observatory (metal-walled garage here). I did all these things in March, and now hope to hold the ambient temperature inside the LRO below 100F all summer.

Now, what to image without TAO? Most people like to see impressive deep sky objects such as nebulae, spiral galaxies (especially), star clusters, and solar system objects such as planets and comets. With less than perfect skies I have another favorite, which few astronomers I know appreciate. When you teach astronomy to kiddies you can point out individual stars like Polaris and Betelgeuse, which they enjoy seeing, and sometimes one can even see colors. Of course with a mid-range telescope these familiar naked-eye stars are very bright, and one can appreciate the star and perhaps its companions, and understand its color. And with a modern camera one can capture both the bright star AND its surrounding field stars; the latter can serve as a good test of focus, as can the bright star with very short (ms-scale) exposures and high magnification. These images can be striking; usually the field stars appear to be more or less randomly scattered, but occasionally a pattern appears that makes you wonder “Who ordered that?” Here I will show two recent images of well-known seasonal naked-eye stars with their field stars, and discuss some of the treasures that one can find on close examination of these images.

Vindemiatrix:

First, a familiar star in early Spring is Vindemiatrix, in Northern Virgo. You can find it in the April Sky Map, and also in the galaxy chart Don Spong provided. The name is clearly classical, and has something to do with this being a good time to gather grapes.

Here I show Vindemiatrix and field stars as captured on 27 Mar 2023, using a stack of 450 4-sec frames at a high gain of 520 / 570 max. Some post processing was used to eliminate stuck pixels and enhance contrast. After plate solving using ASPS I read off coordinates for Vindemiatrix of RA = 13:02:10, Dec +10:57:32 (J2000.0). The French Aladin database confirms these coordinates to this accuracy (+/- 1 unit for each), and quotes a spectroscopic type of G8III-IIIb, a late G yellow-orange giant, consistent with the hue recorded. The Aladin database reminds us that this star is also epsilon Virginis or ϵ Vir, is at a distance of 33.1(2) pc or 108(1) ly, and has a visual (Gaia) magnitude of +2.62 and hence an absolute magnitude of +0.02 (typical for a giant), and is therefore about 80 times solar luminosity. Fun to know.

One's eye is pulled towards the reddish star at upper left; this is the long-period variable KX Vir, mag 7.5, which is a red giant, type M3III, distance 273(3) pc or 890(10) ly. ¹⁵

Enlarging this field and going over it carefully is rewarding; I found several faint “electric blue” stars, one of which Aladin identifies as a “Horizontal Branch” giant, very distant at 5.4(1.0) kpc or 18(3) kly, which has recently augmented its luminosity (and blueness) by initiating He burning in the core. This star is a rather faint 14th magnitude, and is also known as 2MASS J11473066+1441169. If you wish to pursue it, my plate-solver coordinates for this star were RA 11 47 30.7, Dec 14 41 17.

Regulus:

Regulus (alpha Leonis, α Leo) is interesting as one of the least random distributions of field stars that I have encountered. An image of Regulus (a spectroscopic type B8IV subgiant) and field, taken on 27 Feb 2023, is shown below. This is a stack of 240 frames, again 4-sec, with a gain of 520. This distribution of field stars around Regulus appears so far from random that I just have no excuse for it. In any case, I hope you agree that “naked-eye star plus field” as an astronomical image has at least artistic merits, and may deserve more attention than it gets.

Equipment:

My standard equipment is a 190mm Orion Maksutov-Newtonian telescope (which has very nice optics), a CGX mount, a ZWO ASI294MC-P cooled color camera, a ZWO motorized five-position filter wheel, an Orion 50mm guide scope with a ZWOASI290MMmini camera and PHD2 guiding software, and a laser pointer attached to the OTA for when I am totally “lost in space.” For alignment and mount control I use CPWI Telescope Control Software v 2.4.2, and SharpCap v4.0 for image capture, all software (PHD2, CPWI and SharpCap) running on a refurbished Dell Win10 Pro notebook with an external 24” diagonal ASUS monitor. I also use sheets of 1/8” thick rigid dark red plastic for my PC screen and ASUS monitor, to protect night vision. For post processing I use Windows Live Photo Gallery, which suffices for my needs, and to extract image coordinates I use the All-Sky Plate Solver program (ASPS). To access Gaia data and other “serious” astronomical databases I recommend the French CDS interactive sky atlas Aladin (currently v.11). Finally, for planning observing sessions and locating faint asteroids I find the real time sky simulation program TheSkyX to be very helpful.

Units (4 place accuracy where appropriate):

1 parsec (pc) = 3.262 light years (ly).

distance to the center of the galaxy ~ 10 kpc.

speed of light = 1 ly/yr. : -)

1 ly = 63.24 k AU.

1 AU = 149.6 Mkm.

1 nm = 1 nanometer = 10^{-9} m.

H_{α} wavelength = 656.2 nm

+ 1 change in magnitude = 2.512 x fainter.

+ 2.5 change in mag = 10 x fainter.

+ 5 change in mag = 100 x fainter.

R.A. = RA = Right Ascension = angle around the celestial polar axis, in hours, minutes, and seconds.

(analogous to longitude)

Dec = Declination = angle above the celestial equator, in degrees, minutes, and seconds.

(analogous to latitude)

RA and Dec (together with a reference epoch, like J2000.0) specify a star’s position in the sky.

ORION is an amateur science and astronomy group at Oak Ridge, Tennessee that was founded in April 1974 by scientists from the United States Department of Energy facilities at Oak Ridge, Tennessee. We primarily serve the communities of Oak Ridge and Knoxville, and the counties of Anderson, Knox, and Roane.

ORION's mission is to support scientific research, teaching, and amateur astronomy in East Tennessee. We are accordingly closely associated with and support the Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO) through hosting their public events, sharing our knowledge of the skies using a variety of telescopes, and helping to provide intellectually stimulating programs at the observatory. ORION works to share the wonders of the cosmos and the culture of science with people from all walks of life.

ORION members include scientists, engineers, technicians, and others with varied talents and expertise. Over half of ORION members own telescopes, many are amateur radio operators, and some have expertise in astrophotography.

ORION has working relationships with several organizations, including museums and other amateur astronomy groups. Membership is open to individuals who will actively contribute their time and ideas. The annual membership fee is \$20.00, and student discounts are available.

ORION Board and Officers:

President: Don Spong

Vice President and Program Chair:
David Fields

Secretary: Linda Fippin and Noah Frere

Treasurer: Bob Edwards w/ Noah Frere

Trapezium Editor: Ted Barnes

Astrotechnologist: Rob Scott

Videographer: Rob Fowler

Obed Site Outreach and Oak Ridge Star

Parties: Owen Hoffman

We anticipate a great year for Astronomy in 2023! If you have any ideas for programs or activities, please let us know.